

First record of *Ceutorhynchus rusticus* Gyllenhal, 1837 (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) from Altai Krai, Western Siberia

Andrei A. Legalov^{1,2}, Sergei V. Reshetnikov³

1 Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals, SB RAS, Frunze street 11, Novosibirsk, 630091, Russia

2 Altai State University, Lenina 61, Barnaul, 656049, Russia

3 Kropotkina street 273, Novosibirsk, 630111, Russia

Corresponding author: Andrei A. Legalov (fossilweevils@gmail.com)

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Abstract

The first record of *Ceutorhynchus rusticus* Gyllenhal, 1837 (Curculionidae: Conoderinae: Ceutorhynchitae: Ceutorhynchini) from Altai Krai is given. The distribution map, illustrations and redescription of this species are presented. It is the first record from Altai Krai and the most southwestern finding in Siberia.

Keywords

Curculionoidea, Conoderinae, Ceutorhynchini, weevil, fauna, new finding, Siberia

Introduction

The genus *Ceutorhynchus* Germar, 1823 is presented by fifty seven species of this genus were recorded from Siberia (Legalov 2020; Legalov and Reshetnikov 2021) and mostly associated with the family Brassicaceae (Colonnelli 2004). This genus differs from the other genera of the tribe Ceutorhynchini by the curved rostrum

narrower than the profemora, the pronotum base slightly angularly elongate towards the scutellum, and the elytra without spots or stripes of scales.

Ceutorhynchus rusticus Gyllenhal, 1837 is an interesting species characterized by a disjunctive distribution, it lives in Southern Europe and Siberia (Alonso-Zarazaga et al. 2017; Legalov 2020).

This species develops on *Isatis tinctoria* L. (Brassicaceae) in Europe (Rheinheimer and Hassler 2010).

It is the first record of *Ceutorhynchus rusticus* from Altai Krai and the most southwestern finding in Siberia.

Material and methods

Studied specimens are kept in the ISEA – Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals (Russia: Novosibirsk) and CSRN – the private collection of S.V. Reshetnikov (Novosibirsk).

Descriptions and body measuring were performed using a Zeiss Stemi 2000-C dissecting stereomicroscope. The photographs were taken with a camera Fujifilm X-T10.

The terminology of weevil body is according to Lawrence et al. (2010). The systematics of studied taxa are based on Alonso-Zarazaga et al. (2017) and Legalov (2018).

The location of species is shown on map (Fig. 5) which given on original data from collection of the Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals, and also sensu references (Rottenberg 1872; Schultze 1898; Hoffmann 1954; Campobasso et al. 2008; Rheinheimer and Hassler 2010; Angelini 2020; GBIF; etc.).

Results

Superfamily **Curculionoidea** Latreille, 1802

Family **Curculionidae** Latreille, 1802

Subfamily **Conoderinae** Schoenherr, 1833

Supertribe **Ceutorhynchitae** Gistel, 1848

Tribe **Ceutorhynchini** Gistel, 1848

Genus ***Ceutorhynchus*** Germar, 1823

Ceutorhynchus rusticus Gyllenhal, 1837

= *vocifer* Rottenberg, 1871

Figures 1–2

Material. RUSSIA 2 males (CSRN), 1 male (ISEA), 2 females (CSRN), 1 female (ISEA), Altai Krai, Pospelijhinskii District, 6 km NW of Stepnobugrinskii, tract

Voznesenovka, Kizikha River floodplain, 51°34'41.9"N 81°39'36.5"E, on *Lepidium latifolium*, 4.VI.2022, S.V. Reshetnikov; 1 male (ISEA), Mikhailovskii District, 2 km SW of Nikolaevka, 1.V.2018, R.Yu. Dudko; 1 male (ISEA), Altai Republic, Kuray Mountains, 3 km NE of Aktash, Yarlyamry Riv., 50°21' N, 87°41' E, 1550 m, 4.VII.2008, R.Yu. Dudko.

Figure 1. *Ceutorhynchus rusticus* from Altai Krai: a – habitus, male, dorsally; b – habitus, male, laterally; c – thorax, male; d – abdomen, male; e – abdomen, female.

Description. Male. Body black, covered with white, very narrow, appressed brownish scales and rare white quite wide scales, which dense near scutellum, on two last elytral interstices and on bottom. Antennae and sometimes tarsi brownish. Rostrum long, cylindrical, curved, about 1.2 times as long as pronotum, about 6.3 times as long as wide at apex, about 6.9 times as long as wide in middle and at base, finely punctate, almost glabrous at apex, with groove from place of antennal insertion to base. Forehead wide, impressed, densely punctate. Eyes large, rounded, weakly protruding from contour of head, finely faceted. Vertex densely punctate. Temples subequal in length to eye, impressed. Antennae geniculate, quite long,

inserted beyond middle of rostrum. Antennomere 1 elongate-trapezoidal, weakly widened in apical one third, about 8.6 times as long as wide at apex, not reaching eye. Funicle 7-segmented. Antennomeres 2-5 long-conical. Antennomere 2 about 2.8 times as long as wide, about 0.2 times as long as and about 0.7 times as narrow as antennomere 1. Antennomere 3 about 5.3 times as long as wide at apex, slightly longer and about 0.6 times as long as wide of antennomere 2. Antennomere 4 about 3.0 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.6 times as long as and equal in length to antennomere 4. Antennomere 5 2.0 times as long as wide, slightly shorter and wider than antennomere 4. Antennomeres 6-8 suboval. Antennomere 6 about 1.2 times as long as wide, slightly shorter and wider than antennomere 5. Antennomere 7 subequal to antennomere 6. Antennomere 8 about 1.2 times as long as wide at apex, slightly longer and wider than antennomere 7. Club compact, long, 3.0-3.1 times as long as wide in middle, 0.7 times as long as antennomeres 2-8 combined. Pronotum companiform, about 1.3 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.9 times as long as wide in middle and about 0.7 times as long as wide at base, with lateral tubercles. Base slightly angularly elongate towards scutellum. Disc convex, densely, coarsely punctate, with distinct medial longitudinal groove. Distance between punctures smaller than puncture diameter. Pronotal constriction distinct. Sides of pronotum convex medially. Scutellum convex, small, quite narrow. Elytra quite wide, about 1.2 times as long as wide at base and in middle, about 1.4 times as long as wide in apical quarter, about 2.1 times as long as pronotum. Humeri convex. Striae regular. Interstriae wide, flattened, 3.3-4.0 times as wide as striae, punctate. Apices of elytra rounded separately. Prosternum with distinct postocular lobes and rostral channel. Procoxal portion of prosternum about 0.8 times as long as procoxal length. Postcoxal portion of prosternum about 0.4 times as long as procoxal length. Metacoxal cavities separated. Mesepimeron enlarged, visible between bases of prosternum, elytra, covered with wide scales. Metacoxal cavities dilated, separated by apex of ventrite 2. Metaventrite convex, about 1.8 times as long as metacoxa. Metanepisternum wide, punctate, about 2.3 times as long as wide in middle. Abdomen convex, punctate. Ventrite 1 1.5 times as long as metacoxal length. Ventrite 2 0.9 times as long as ventrite 1. Ventrite 3 0.8 times as long as ventrite 2. Ventrite 4 0.7 times as long as ventrite 3. Ventrite 5 2.0 times as long as ventrite 4, impressed. Pygidium exposed, with median longitudinal deep groove. Legs long. Femora weakly clavate, punctate, with small tooth. Tibiae weakly curved, weakly flattened. Meso- and metatibiae with small mucro. Tarsi long, with pulvilli on underside. Tarsomeres 1 and 2 long-conical. Tarsomere 3 bilobed. Tarsomere 5 elongate. Claws large, free, with teeth. Body length: 4.1-4.2 mm. Rostrum length: 1.2-1.3 mm. Female. Rostrum narrower, about 1.3 times as long as pronotum, about 7.2 times as long as wide at apex, about 8.0 times as long as wide in middle and at base. Pronotum about 1.3 times as long as wide at apex, about 0.8 times as long as wide in middle and at base. Elytra about 1.2 times as long as wide at base and about 1.1 times as long as wide in middle, about 1.4 times as long as wide in apical quarter, about 2.0 times as long as pronotum. Ventrite 1 about 1.6 times as long as metacoxal length. Ventrite 2 about 0.7 times as

long as ventrite 1. Ventrite 3 about 0.7 times as long as ventrite 2. Ventrite 4 equal in length to ventrite 3. Ventrite 5 1.5 times as long as ventrite 4, with weak median longitudinal groove. Pygidium with median longitudinal weak groove. Meso- and metatibiae without mucro. Body length: 4.1 mm. Rostrum length: 1.4 mm.

Remarks. This species was collected on the river bank (Fig. 3) on *Lepidium latifolium* (Fig. 4).

Distribution. Europe, Caucasus, Western Siberia (Fig. 5).

Figure 2. *Ceutorhynchus rusticus* from Altai Krai, aedeagus: a –dorsally; b – laterally.

Figure 3. Habitat of *Ceutorhynchus rusticus*.

Figure 4. Collection plant of *Ceutorhynchus rusticus*.

Figure 5. Distribution of *Ceutorhynchus rusticus*.

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